

D7.2 One Health SRIA 2021-2030 - Preliminary Outline

WP 7 Sustainability

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: SVA, Sciensano, BfR, RIVM

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

Introduction

The OHEJP Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) is a strategy document which describes the sustainability of the OHEJP after the end of the programme. The SRIA is based on the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) and it uses additional internal and external documents and sources of information. A part of the first steps in the process to develop the SRIA was the establishment of a core group with representatives from WP1, WP2, WP5 and WP7. The group elaborated an outline that shows the constituent parts/elements of the SRIA. This outline is presented in this deliverable. A more in-depth description of each of the points in the outline and the sources of information to be used for the development and writing of each point is being prepared. The complete and final SRIA will be presented at the end of the OHEJP (D7.5 Final SRIA, due month 60). This late completion of the SRIA will allow the inclusion of the latest information and updates until the end of the OHEJP.

One Health SRIA 2021- 2030 - Preliminary Outline Constituent parts of the SRIA:

1. Introduction

- 1.1. The past: background and context, introduction of the OHEJP
- 1.2. The present: setting the scene based on today's situation and conditions
- 1.3. The future: how this SRIA will address the actual needs of stakeholders in the future

2. Vision and mission

3. Objectives

- 3.1. The six OHEJP specific objectives (SRA)
- 3.2. Additional objectives of the SRIA

4. Expected impacts

5. Priority research and integrative topics/themes or R&I priority areas

5.1. Topic/area AMR

- 5.1.1. Introduction, rationale, challenges
- 5.1.2. R&I objectives
- 5.1.3. Activities that will ensure sustainability in the future
- 5.1.4. Synergies and external (outside OHEJP) links with JPIAMR, and other relevant initiatives
- 5.1.5. Outcomes
- 5.1.6. Expected Impacts

5.2. Topic area One Health

- 5.2.1. Introduction, rationale, challenges
- 5.2.2. R&I objectives
- 5.2.3. Activities that will ensure sustainability in the future
- 5.2.4. Synergies and links
- 5.2.5. Outcomes
- 5.2.6. Impacts

5.3. The environment and climate change, preparedness, emerging threats and others

- 6. Cross cutting issues and horizontal activities
- 7. Drivers and enablers
- 8. Implementation plan or Road map for the SRIA
- 9. Synergies and complementarities of the SRIA (in general, besides the specific ones under each topic area)
- 10. Dissemination
- 11. Next steps: what the SRIA can be used for
- 12. References/selected bibliographies

Title of the section	Contents to be developed in the section	Source and materials to write the section
1. Introduction		
1.1 The past: background and context (Introduction of OHEJP)	<p>- background and context, introduce and describe shortly the OHEJP, including how the needs of national and international stakeholders were identified and addressed and what OHEJP has delivered</p> <p>-the 6 objectives are still relevant, the SRIA will address them</p> <p>-updates: since the start of OHEJP new partners, new stakeholders, identified needs of stakeholders, selection of outcomes that are particularly relevant to sustain in the future, for example refer to COVID-19 work done/in progress</p>	<p>SRA (sections Introduction and About), (6 specific objectives under Vision)+ new text.</p> <p>https://onehealthejp.eu/#-outcomes</p>
1.2 The present: setting the scene based on today's situation and conditions:	-Current challenges, issues, new key policy developments, current needs	<p>-SRA (section the challenge in introduction) + new text</p> <p>-Contribution from WP2: monitoring scientific developments, screening of relevant publications, etc</p> <p>strategic developments monitored by UCM -SWOT analysis</p> <p>-WP5 Scan Stakeholders documents: policy needs/gaps + Relevant policies (focusing on the upcoming and most recent ones)</p>

<p>1.3 The future: how this SRIA will address the actual needs of stakeholders in the future</p>	<p>-Rationale</p> <p>-What will be the actual needs of stakeholders after OHEJP? Evolving process, updates will be needed according to changes</p> <p>-Address key policies and strategies that will be important in the future</p>	<p>-Conditions and needs identified in 1.1 and 1.2 as a base. For example, COVID added to preparedness</p> <p>-Policy and strategy documents, for ex. Farm to Fork, Green Deal, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, etc</p>
<p>2. Vision and mission</p>	<p>-The aspiration/ambition of the SRIA</p> <p>-Short-sharp long-term vision for the SRIA</p> <p>-Follow up the vision in SRA “Towards a shared landscape” and “The overarching ambition” (create a sustainable European framework)</p> <p>-To further build and consolidate the Med-Vet-Net consortium</p> <p>-To maintain available the outcomes of One Health</p> <p>Mission: Consolidate and expand the European consortium on One Health; thus creating a recognized OH partner in Europe</p>	<p>-SRA</p>
<p>3. Objectives</p>		
<p>3.1 OHEJP specific objectives</p>	<p>-The 6 SRA specific objectives mentioned in the introduction (section 1.1) are discussed here from the current and future perspective, which ones are important/realistic to sustain after OHEJP?</p> <p>-Will the impact of the objectives achieved continue in the future?</p> <p>-Their sustainability-what will be done after 2023</p>	<p>6 objectives in SRA, section Vision</p>
<p>3.2 Additional objectives of the SRIA</p>	<p>Based on scanning done under preparation of this SRIA and on results of OHEJP additional objectives will arise. How will this SRIA address their sustainability?</p> <p>-Role of the environment</p> <p>-Possible release of permafrost viruses due to global warming</p> <p>-Role of new breeding techniques in animal production (change in wildlife/ domestic animals relationships)</p> <p>-Vector borne zoonoses</p> <p>-Water borne zoonoses</p> <p>-Emerging Infectious Diseases</p> <p>-Preparedness</p>	<p>Role of the environment. Source: Thematic report on environmental issues.</p> <p>UN Sustainable goals</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Address UN Sustainable goals -Identify opportunities: Horizon Europe, MVNA, others -Place the OHEJP Consortium on the EU scene, as a privileged partner. 	
4. Expected impacts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Strong One Health approach to prevent, detect and control zoonoses/ emerging zoonoses, AMR - Support to national, EU, and international policy initiatives -List and develop expected impacts and give KPI whenever possible, for example number of publications 	
5. Priority research and integrative topics/themes (and sub-themes) or R&I priority areas	-Here describe the priority research and integrative topics/themes (and sub-themes) or R&I priority areas, which ones are they and why are they prioritized?	<p>SRA, section Priority topics and Activities, + additional text</p> <p>Input from WP2, gap analysis and updated research priorities through elicitation of partners</p> <p>SWAT analysis</p>
5.1 Topic/area AMR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1.1. Introduction, rationale, challenges 5.1.2. R&I objectives 5.1.3. Activities that will ensure sustainability in the future 5.1.4. Synergies and external (outside OHEJP) links with JPIAMR, and other relevant initiatives 5.1.5. Outcomes 5.1.6. Expected Impacts 	From Module AMR
5.2 Topic area One Health Cross collaborative work multidisciplinary (define)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.2.1. Introduction, rationale, challenges 5.2.2. R&I objectives 5.2.3. Activities that will ensure sustainability in the future 5.2.4. Synergies and links 5.2.5. Outcomes 5.2.6. Impacts 	From module OH
5.3 Other topic areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Shorter/less elaborated than 5.2 and 5.1. -Environment: wildlife hosts, ecosystems, vectors, changes in ecosystems, wildlife management, 	

	<p>climate change, environmental changes affecting human and animal health, etc</p> <p>-Preparedness: introduction showing what encompasses preparedness (vaccines, contingency planning, early warning, prevention, etc) and then explain on which part we focus on in this SRIA, role of this SRIA in preparedness. Explain expertise of OHEJP in preparedness</p> <p>-Emerging threats</p>	
6. Cross-cutting issues/horizontal activities , complexities, needs for integrated and holistic approach, matrices	<p>-Consolidating interactions with stakeholders.</p> <p>-International aspects beyond EU.</p> <p>-Linking with initiatives like PREZODE and others.</p>	
7. Drivers and enablers	<p>-Political situation ("everybody" is talking about One Health")</p> <p>-Obj WP7 OHEJP: " To assess drivers and constraints for institutionalisation of a sustainable EJP".</p>	
8. Implementation plan (or Road map or work plan) for the SRIA	<p>-Activities and timeline - Focus on activities that will lead to ensuring sustainability</p> <p>-Based on the achievements of the One Health EJP identify what should be taken up (by the MVNA) and what not; define the partners (for instance: 'all with interest in cross-sector collaboration': NRL, EURL, research institutes, ministries, funding organisations, international organizations, existing networks, etc.) and the objectives (explore possibilities for collaborative research, networking, integrative activities, E&T, etc.)</p> <p>-Explore and present alternatives for funding: partnerships under Horizon Europe , WP calls under Horizon Europe, cluster 6 and Health, maybe others.</p>	<p>SRA, sections Activities, Structure + new activities</p> <p>This may be placed under implementation plan, or activities</p>
9. Synergies and complementarities	<p>-In general, besides the specific ones under each topic area</p> <p>-Links with other JPI or relevant initiatives, European Partnerships,</p>	

	<p>AH&W, OH-AMR, Food Systems, Pandemic Preparedness</p> <p>-Links with work programme under HE</p> <p>-Links with PREZODE, ERRAZE, ZODIAC, Epizone, STAR-IDAZ, CWG, MedVetNet</p>	
10. Dissemination	-To whom and how will this SRIA be disseminated	
11. Next steps: what the SRIA can be used for, conclusions	<p>-Needs of stakeholders</p> <p>-For various target groups, EC, researchers, policymakers, funding bodies, enterprises, general public.</p> <p>- Relation between Vision 2030, SRIA and implementation plan</p> <p>-As input to the SRIA of the PAH&W</p> <p>- This part could close the circle: at the beginning we have a description of what policies will be important in the future (section "setting the scene"), then the SRIA itself, then at the end how those policies could take advantage of the SRIA</p>	<p>WP5 identified needs of stakeholders</p> <p>-Policy event</p>
6 References/selected bibliographies		